

Short name	MRV methodologies	Long name	Lack of harmonised framework for monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV)
Geographical scope	National + International		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of internationally developed, and adopted MRV framework • Those MRV methodologies that are available are limited in terms of geographical scope, activity types or linkage to specific market mechanisms/regulatory frameworks • Building upon and harmonizing best practices • Environmental integrity principles need to be at the center of these methodologies 		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCS+ initiative working on internationally available (under Verra's VCS) MRV framework • Available methodologies to date also differ in terms of their quality: environmental integrity vs. practicality 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MRV Readiness • Liability in hubs 		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poralla, M.; Honegger, M.; Gameros, C. et al. (2022): Tracking greenhouse gas removals: baseline and monitoring methodologies, additionality testing, and accounting, NET-Rapido Consortium and Perspectives Climate Research, London, UK and Freiburg i.B., Germany • Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2019): 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories • Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2006): 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories 		